

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B136
Date: 29 Sep 2005
Take Off 07:40:22 12:12:50
Landing: 10:38:01 16:58:14
Flight Time 2h57m39 4h45m24

Campaign: AMPEP
Operating Area: Grand round-Britain tour

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Eiko Nemitz	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	CCN	Stuart Heath	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Filters	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	WAS	Jim Hopkins	York University
10	AMS	James Allan	University of Manchester
11	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
12	PTRMS	Jennifer Murphy	UEA
13	Bag Filler 1	Alan McDonald	CEH
14	Bag Filler 2	Daniela Famulari	CEH
15	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
16			

Flight Track:

B136 Track 29-SEP-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B136
 Date: 29 Sep 2005
 Project: AMPEP
 Location: Round Britain flight

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
071919		INU	0.22 kft	126	to nav 52' 04.36N 0' 37.48W
074022		T/O	6.4 kft	354	Cranfield
074810		level fl100	10.0 kft	246	noxy calcs
075255		nev zero	10.0 kft	248	
075619		JW zero	10.0 kft	260	
081427		HORACE	10.0 kft	258	complete system restart
081507	081926	Profile 1	10.0 - 6.0 kft	258	
081750		horace	7.5 kft	258	1260
081926	082049	Run 1	6.0 kft	252	
082049	082257	Profile 2	6.0 - 4.0 kft	252	
082257	082411	Run 2	4.0 kft	260	
082411	082647	Profile 3	4.0 - 1.8 kft	267	
082647	082813	Run 3	1.8 - 1.7 kft	265	
082813	082947	Profile 4	1.7 - 0.25 kft	291	
082948	083056	Run 4	0.22 - 0.24 kft	289	
083056	083128	Profile 5	0.24 - -.01 kft	288	
083128	083229	Run 5	-.01 - 0.02 kft	288	
083406	095851	Run 6	0.77 - 0.93 kft	355	
083451		qnh 1023	0.74 kft	354	1000ft towards wp50
083542		horace	0.74 kft	357	5544
083551		wp50	0.75 kft	357	
084103		qnh 1022	0.76 kft	357	
084515		horace	0.75 kft	356	process & drs check
084854		wp 51	0.76 kft	000	
085218		qnh 1021	0.76 kft	000	
090457		qnh 1020	0.80 kft	359	
091121		horace	0.84 kft	000	process & drs check
091131		qnh 1019	0.83 kft	000	
091711		qnh 1018	0.87 kft	000	
092327		wp 60	0.87 kft	335	
092420		video	0.86 kft	332	ffc & dfc #2 started
093611		wp 61	0.85 kft	321	
093659		horace	0.88 kft	311	process & drs
093809		qnh 1017	0.89 kft	311	
094706		abeam wp 62	0.92 kft	341	
095852	100004	Profile 6	0.93 - 0.19 kft	006	
100004	100105	Run 7	0.19 - 0.20 kft	004	
100105	100723	Profile 7	0.20 - 6.5 kft	355	
100723	100829	Run 8	6.5 kft	042	
100829		Profile 8	6.5	051	not flown as profile
101015		fl100	10.0 kft	045	noxy cal
103801		Land	0.07 kft	276	Inverness
104329		gps	0.07 kft	276	57'32.45 N 4'03.71 W
104451		inu	0.07 kft	276	57 32.63 N 4 06.15 W
105404		inu	0.07 kft	307	to align
115934		inu	0.06 kft	276	to nav
122051		fl100	10.0 kft	046	noxy calcs
121250		T/O	10.0 kft	047	Inverness
123411	123644	descent	9.6 - 6.0 kft	049	to fl 60
123644	123746	Run 9	6.0 kft	047	fl 60
123746	124619	Profile 9	6.0 - 0.29 kft	048	
123929		video	4.7 kft	048	ffc & dfc #3 started
124130		interrupt	3.1 kft	049	profile 9
124301		recommence	3.1 kft	261	Profile 9
124619	124728	Run 10	0.29 - 0.38 kft	192	
124740		climb	0.60 kft	192	to 1000
124809	155425	Run 11	1.1 - 0.67 kft	190	
124933		nev zero	1.1 kft	191	
125026		JW zero	1.1 kft	191	

125611		qnh 1013	1.0 kft	192
125812		wp 75	1.0 kft	189
130543		qnh	0.97 kft	184 1015
131402		horace	1.00 kft	177 process & drs check
132430		qnh	0.94 kft	181 1016
132710		abeam wp 76	0.96 kft	181
133340		qnh	0.92 kft	170 1017
133711		video	0.94 kft	169 ffc & dfc #4 started
133954		qnh	0.91 kft	170 1018
134817		wp 79	0.91 kft	146
135638		qnh	0.89 kft	145 1019
140137		qnh	0.87 kft	153 1020
140256		wp 80	0.85 kft	154
141835		qnh	0.77 kft	139 1021
142659		wp 40	0.82 kft	153
143942		video	0.80 kft	187 ffc & dfc #5 started
144214		wp 41	0.78 kft	199
144410		qnh	0.75 kft	198 1023
145111		qnh	0.71 kft	199 1024
145441		wp 42	0.73 kft	220
150547		qnh	0.72 kft	240 1025
150706		wp 43	0.69 kft	255
152327		wp 44	0.69 kft	250
153500		qnh	0.68 kft	227 1026
153831		wp 45	0.67 kft	259
154226		qnh	0.68 kft	268 1027
154337		video	0.66 kft	270 ffc & dfc #6 started
155426	155524	Profile 10	0.67 - -.05 kft	314
155524	155625	Run 12	-.03 - -.04 kft	315
155625	160049	Profile 11	0.58 - 4.7 kft	309
160050	160857	Run 13	4.7 - 4.6 kft	314
160858	161245	Profile 12	4.6 - 0.71 kft	312
161246	162352	Run 14	0.71 - 0.72 kft	354
161322		qnh	0.72 kft	005 1024
162438		climb	2.9 kft	048 to fl100
162757		fl100	10.0 kft	043 noxy cals
165814		Land	0.12 kft	308 Cranfield
170301		INU	0.12 kft	307 52 04.56 N 0 40.31 W

B136 Track 29-SEP-05

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B136

Mission Scientist: Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Date : 29-September-2005

Outline schedule:

05:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
07:00 – Briefing
08:00 – Clear aircraft and security check
08:15 – Doors close
08:45 – Take off Cranfield
11:35 – Land Inverness
13:00 – Take off Inverness
18:00 – Land Cranfield
18:30 – Debrief
20:00 – Power down

Location: A clockwise circum-navigation of Great Britain, cutting off the North West of Scotland and Cornwall

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the UK in a westerly airflow over the UK. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying around British Mainland, beginning with a transit at FL100 to the operating area (flown at increased speed), followed by a descent into the Bristol Channel to sample some background air at the normal flight height of about 1000ft. The flight will then proceed north to sample the outflow from Ireland and to characterize the air entering the British Mainland, into a space off the West Coast of Scotland that is unaffected by Ireland. After an ascending profile the flight will commence NE at FL100 for a refueling stop in Inverness. After refueling, FL100 will be re-attained in NE direction, followed by a descending profile which will finish off the NE tip of British Mainland. The flight will then follow the East and West coast clockwise before an ascending profile is flown in northward direction just off Plymouth. The flight will finish with a transit at FL100 back to Cranfield. Vertical profiles will be stepped over the range 250 to 6000 ft, with 1 m each at 250, 500, 2000, 4000 and 6000 ft and should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO. These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

Flight leg 136a

- a) Take off Cranfield 08:45 (may get delayed until 9:00 depending on availability of CAT6 fire cover) and climb to FL100 for transit to operating area, towards waypoint 49 in the Bristol Channel, at increased speed (250); NO_x calibration.

- b) T+40: Stepped profile descent (6000, 4000, 2000, 500, 250) over Irish Sea to 1000 ft as soon as NOxy calibration is finished, followed by boundary layer (1000ft) flight North; Ireland filter pack run
- c) T+125: Stepped up profile N of WP 71
- d) T+140: Climb to FL100 for NOxy calibration
- e) T+170: Land Inverness

Flight leg 136b

- a) Take off Inverness 13:00 (delay of refueling possible), ascend to FL100 for transit NE (NOxy calibration)
- b) T+25: Stepped-down profile (6000, 4000, 2000, 500, 250) to point A, re-assume 1000 ft
- c) T+220: Stepped-up profile at Devon coast (250, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000), crossing of Devon towards Bristol Channel
- d) T+240: Transit back to Cranfield at FL100 (NOxy calibration) (potential brief boundary layer leg in Bristol Channel, depending on timing)
- e) T+300: Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 – Alan Roberts
2. Pilot 2 – Ian Ramsay-Rae
3. CCM – Doug Anderson
4. CCM2/CCN – Stuart Heath
5. Core Chemistry – Ruth Purvis
6. Cloud Physics – Martyn Pickering
7. Flight Manager – Jim Crawford
8. Mission Scientist – Eiko Nemitz
9. Bag Sampling 1 – Alan McDonald
10. Bag Sampling 2 – Daniela Famulari
11. Filters – Bob Wells
12. AMS – James Allan
13. NOxy – Dave Stewart
14. PTRMS – Jennifer Murphy
15. WAS – Jim Hopkins

EGTC -> EGPE - Overview
 NavData Cycle 2005-10 Expires: Thursday, 27 October 2005.
 Scale: 1:2923276 (1 inch = 40.09 naut mi). Printed on 28 Sep 2005

JEPPESEN
FliteStar 9.150

EGPE -> EGTC - Overview
 NavData Cycle 2005-10 Expires: Thursday, 27 October 2005.
 Scale: 1:4105248 (1 inch = 56.30 naut mi). Printed on 28 Sep 2005

JEPPESEN
FliteStar 9.150

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value.

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at 1000ft.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: N/A

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO, NO_{xy}(HNO₃)

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.136**.....

 Date **29/09/2005**.....

 Page **1** of **6**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		Greenland			cloudless sky; some cirrus to NE
7:45	F10				no cloud
7:47		FL100			start of noisy cut. wind 14 m/s @ 309°
					NO ₂ profile on F10 suggest RL height of 600m
7:56					scattered cirrus
8:08					patch of broken strat - cumulus
8:15	F1	FL100			→ 6000 ft.
8:19	R1	@ 6000 ft			at Wake coast some strato at coast
8:20	R2	6000 - 4000			
					partly cloud top 5000 ft
8:23	R2	@ 4000 ft			flying below clouds but avoiding them
8:24	P3	4000 → 2000 ft			cloud base @ 3000 ft
8:26	R3	2000 ft			8 m/s @ 307° or 17 km @ 309°
8:27		WP 49			broken cloud; hazy horizon
8:28	P4	2000 → 500			
8:29	R4	500 ft			
8:30	P5	500 → 250			
8:31	R5	250 ft			5 m/s @ 304°
8:33		WP	50		
8:34	R6	long	1000 ft		an
8:34:10	Fibres	1	start		
8:42					wind 3 m/s @ 288° or 16 km @ 288°
					0.2 ppb SO ₂ & 0.4 ppb NO ₂
8:48					small plume ship of Ireland? WP 51

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.136a**

 Date **29/09/2005**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
8:53		07kft	0°		wind 4 m/s @ 263° / 17 knots @ 281°
8:58					CO & CN rising, NO ₂ also (SE of Dublin)
9:00		wind			6 m/s @ 287° / 23 knots @ 285°
9:02					Dublin plane?
					also some slipping Dublin / Liverpool or Holyhead
9:22					Belfast plane?
9:23			WP 60		12 m/s @ 279°
9:28					level with plant on shore 11 m/s @ 267°
					blow to NE
9:35					spots of rain/droplets at WP 61
9:38	FP1				level of sea
9:39	FP2				start of sea
					very low conc of CN
9:41					spike in NO _x 10 m/s @ 280° brief precip. from start to E
9:58	PG		1000 → 250		end of FT Run 3
10:00	R7		@ 250		
10:01	PT		250 → 6000 ft		
					broken cloud base @ 2000 ft, top @ 4500 ft.
	R8		@ 6500 ft		high CN counts
10:42					land Turbance

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**.....B366.....

 Date 29/09/2005.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	T6	Increase			broken cloud (4500 - 8000 ft)
					localized showers
12:20		start of N2O ₂ cal		@ FL100	
12:36	R9			FL60, moving above clouds from cloudless area	
12:37	R9			FL60 → 2500ft	broken cloud 4500 -
				wind 10m/s 286° / 24@296°	
12:46	R10			@ 250 ft	scattered cloud
12:48	R11			start of FP Run 3	@ 1000 ft.
12:52				winds 5 m/s @ 287°	
12:53				oily upwiral	→ spike in NO ₂
12:57				wp 75	
13:00				some fading, boats upwiral & increased CN & NO _x .	
13:03		east of Freresburg			wind 8 m/s @ 281°
13:06		Petroleum with fire plume & power plant (not operating?)			
		high NO _x & CN			
13:08		showers in distance to west			some drizzle in flight path
13:09		some drizzle again; further showers to the west			
13:12		again a little drizzle; CO & NO ₂ increasing			
13:23		end of FP Run 3			
13:24		wind		9 m/s @ 270°	
13:25		start FP Run 4			
13:28		central cell plume			
13:32		plume increasing			↓ 6 ppb SO ₂ !

Mission Scientist's Log

1. WP 79 - 2
 2. WP 8 bottles fill problem
 → 16 bottles not available!

Flight No **B. 136**.....

Date **29/09/2005**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:40					wind 8 w/s @ 300°
13:42		fire plume visible			near Teeside? W of Newcastle
13:48					⇒ deflected 13:40?
13:48		WP 79			Newcastle plume ?
13:57					Teeside plume ?
					Cement works ?
13:53		wind 8 w/s @		303°	
14:02			9 w/s @	290°	/ 176 @ 288°
14:03		end FP Run 4			
14:06		start FP Run 5			
14:12		Humbly Grove plume			
14:17		wind 13 w/s @		285°	/ 16 @ 314°
14:22		temporary increase to 300 ft due to encroaching low flying aircraft			
14:23		scattered cloud to east, broken cloud to west.			
14:26		WP 80			
14:31		aggravated VOC & particles, high NO ₂			spots of rain
		not clear where this plume comes from			(west of Newcastle)
14:33		wind 11 w/s @		295°	(near Lowestoft)
14:41		ships possibly contributing to NO _x			
14:43		FP Run 5 finish			
14:46		FP Run 6 start			
14:52		London plume?			Wind 10 w/s @ 296°
14:54		Del 42 in front of Dover			
		considerable			

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.136b**

 Date **29/09/2005**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:58					still London outflow wind keeping up at 9m/s @ 30°
15:06	WP 43				wind 8 m/s @ 291°
15:13					Avonmouth plume? high overcast
15:15					scattered cloud in English Channel 5m/s @ 304°
15:20					downwind of small ^{wind} plume
15:23					plume from chimneys near Southampton?
15:20					FP Run 6 finish
15:23					FP 7 start
15:35					ship plume?
15:38					WP 45
15:48					concentrations of NO _x & SO ₂ (not col) increasing in westerly flow 9 m/s @ 262° wind direction shifted from NW to SW; getting some European recirculation?
15:51					increasing cloud & poorer visibility
15:54					WP 46
15:54	R11				end of run
15:54	P10	1000			→ 250 ft
15:55	R12				@ 250 ft
15:56	P11	250			→ 5000 ft (penetrating scattered cloud @ 2300 ft → 4000 ft) + overcast by high-level cloud.
16:00	R13				@ 5000 ft
16:08	R13				end of run

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B136

Date : 29 Sep 2005

Operator and contact info : Ruth Purvis (rupu@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	
O₃	
NO_x	
SO₂	
TDLAS	N/A
WAS	See WAS operator

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
Shorter (quick cal) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
8:13	FL100	
8:36	1000ft	
9:12	1000ft	
9:41	1000ft	
12:28	1000ft	
12:51	1000ft	
13:22	1000ft	
14:06	1000ft	
15:05	1000ft	
15:39	1000ft	
16:15	1000ft	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B136

Date: 10/05/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:15:01	15	0.07	0								Start profile 1 from FL100
08:16:09	10	0.06									FL090
08:17:14	15	0.06									FL080
08:18:16	30	0.06									FL070
08:19:26	40	0.06									End P1 & Start Run 1 @ FL060
08:20:00	35	0.06									
08:20:48	35	0.06									End of Run 1 Start P2
08:22:05	45	0.07									FL050
08:22:54	44	0.07									End P2 Start Run 2 @ FL040
08:23:00	40	0.07									
08:24:15	45	0.07									End Run 2 Start P3
08:25:18	55	0.07									FL030
08:26:43	Noise										End P3 Start Run 3 @ 2000'
08:27:00	Noise										
08:28:20	80	0.06									End Run 3 Start P4
08:29:08	Noise										1000'
08:29:46	Noise										End P4 Start Run 4 @ 500'
08:30:00	Noise										
08:30:55	Noise										End Run 4 Start P5
08:31:26	Noise										End of P5 Start Run 5 @ 250'
08:32:00	Noise										
08:32:35											End of Run 5 Start P6
08:34:06											End P6 Start Run 6 @ 1000'
08:35:00	Noise		1								
08:37:00	Noise										
08:39:00	180	0.06									
08:41:00	110	0.06									
08:43:00	Noise										
08:45:00	110	0.06									
08:47:00	Noise										
08:49:00	Noise										
08:51:00	Noise										
08:53:00	Noise										
08:55:00	Noise										

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B136

Date: 10/05/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:57:00	120	0.06	2								
08:59:00	95	0.06									
09:01:00	110	0.06									
09:03:00	110	0.06									
09:05:00	120	0.06									
09:07:00	90	0.06									
09:09:00	85	0.06									
09:11:00	75	0.06									
09:13:00	70	0.06									
09:15:00	70	0.06									
09:17:00	90	0.06									
09:19:00	75	0.06									
09:21:00	100	0.06									
09:23:00	90	0.06	3								
09:25:00	130	0.06									
09:27:00	100	0.06									
09:29:00	70	0.06									
09:31:00	70	0.06									
09:33:00	80	0.06									
09:35:00	110	0.06	5		2	600	1	1000	600	12	
09:37:00	70	0.06									
09:39:00	70	0.06									
09:41:00	80	0.06									
09:43:00	100	0.06									
09:45:00	120	0.06									
09:47:00	95	0.06									
09:49:00	70	0.06									
09:51:00	70	0.06									
09:53:00	45	0.06									
09:55:00	50	0.06									
09:58:49	45	0.06									End of Run 6 Start Profile 6
10:00:01	40	0.06	6								End of P6 Start Run 7 @ 250'
10:01:08											End Run 7 Start P7 from 250'

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B136

Date: 10/05/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:01:55	30	0.06	6								FL010
10:02:47	20	0.06									FL020
10:03:49	15	0.06									FL030
10:04:50	10	0.06									FL040
10:05:45	5	0.06									FL050
10:07:22	5	0.06									End of P 7 Start Run 8 @ FL065
10:08:00	10	0.06									
10:08:35											End of Run 8
12:36:46											Start Run 9 @ FL060
12:37:00	25	0.06	13								
12:37:50											End of Run 9 Start P9 from FL060
12:39:05	20	0.06									FL050
12:40:16	50	0.06									FL040
12:41:27	35	0.06									FL030
12:44:10	35	0.06	14		Noise						2000'
12:45:30	40	0.06									1000'
12:46:15											End of P9 start Run 10 @ 250'
12:47:00	40	0.06									
12:47:20											End of Run 10
12:48:16											Start Run 11 @ 1000'
12:49:00	55	0.06									
12:51:00	50	0.06									
12:53:00	45	0.06									
12:55:00	60	0.06									
12:57:00	50	0.06									
12:59:00	60	0.06									
13:01:00	80	0.06									
13:03:00	70	0.06									
13:05:00	60	0.06									
13:07:00	100	0.06									
13:09:00	70	0.06						10	600	12	
13:11:00	85	0.06	15								
13:13:00	170	0.08	19		20	800	1	1000	2000	1	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B136

Date: 10/05/05

Operator: MAP

Page 4 of 7

G.M.T.		PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit		
13:15:00	85	0.06	19									
13:17:00	65	0.06										
13:19:00	65	0.06										
13:21:00	50	0.06										
13:23:00	65	0.06										
13:25:00	60	0.06										
13:27:00	100	0.06										
13:29:00	110	0.06										
13:31:00	85	0.06										
13:33:00	150	0.06										
13:35:00	230	0.06										
13:37:00	115	0.06										
13:39:00	110	0.06										
13:41:00	85	0.06										
13:43:00	75	0.06										
13:45:00	75	0.06	20									
13:47:00	95	0.06										
13:49:00	105	0.06										
13:51:00	95	0.06										
13:53:00	105	0.06										
13:55:00	115	0.06										
13:57:00	185	0.06										
13:59:00	125	0.06										
14:01:00	90	0.06										
14:03:00	70	0.06										
14:05:00	80	0.06										
14:07:00	105	0.06										
14:09:00	170	0.06										
14:11:00	200	0.06										
14:13:00	175	0.06										
14:15:00	150	0.06										
14:17:00	170	0.06										
14:19:00	175	0.06										

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B136

Date: 10/05/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:21:00	250	0.06	20								
14:23:00	300	0.06									
14:25:00	305	0.06									
14:27:00	300	0.06									
14:29:00	380	0.07									
14:31:00	600	0.07									
14:33:00	540	0.07	21								
14:35:00	540	0.07									
14:37:00	540	0.07									
14:39:00	490	0.07									
14:41:00	380	0.07									
14:43:00	390	0.07									
14:45:00	400	0.07									
14:47:00	240	0.06									
14:49:00	190	0.06									
14:51:00	175	0.06									
14:53:00	180	0.06									
14:55:00	225	0.06									
14:57:00	320	0.06									
14:59:00	250	0.09									
15:01:00	240	0.09									
15:03:00	160	0.09									
15:05:00	140	0.09									
15:07:00	120	0.06									
15:09:00	140	0.06									
15:11:00	270	0.06									
15:13:00	280	0.07									
15:15:00	330	0.07									
15:17:00	285	0.07	22								
15:19:00	160	0.06									
15:21:00	420	0.07									
15:23:00	180	0.06									
15:25:00	400	0.07									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B136

Date: 10/05/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	
15:27:00	260	0.07	22								
15:29:00	145	0.06									
15:31:00	175	0.07									
15:33:00	190	0.07									
15:35:00	200	0.06									
15:37:00	145	0.06									
15:39:00	100	0.06	23								
15:41:00	85	0.06									
15:43:00	85	0.06									
15:45:00	85	0.06									
15:47:00	80	0.06									
15:49:00	60	0.06	24								
15:51:00	55	0.06									
15:53:00	55	0.06									
15:53:30											End of Run 11
15:54:30											Start profile 10 from 1000'
15:55:27											End of P10 start Run 12 @ 250'
15:56:00	45	0.06									
15:56:35											End of Run 12 Start P11
15:57:40	55	0.06									FL010
15:58:18	65	0.06									FL020
15:59:17	55	0.06	25								FL030
16:00:08	55	0.06									FL040
16:00:54											End of P11 Start Run 13 @ 5000'
16:01:00	35	0.06									
16:03:00	100	0.06									
16:05:00	80	0.06									
16:07:00	100	0.06						100	600	12	
16:09:00											End of Run 13
16:09:02											Start Profile 12
16:09:45	110	0.06	26			1		15			FL040
16:10:40	65	0.06									FL030
16:11:30	85	0.06									FL020

CCN LOG

1 of 4

ALLEVIATOR GMT	ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS	
					1	2	3	4	5		
080941	081015		100 FL		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
				18.67	0.54	0.79	1.19	1.55	2.26	S	descended
				18.60	165	261	272	364	452	D	on 5 sat
				18.58	159	162	167	170	170	B	no Px or temp
				18.55	2357	2378	2388	2384	2387	R	data from
				18.51	965.1	965.2	965.2	965.2	965.8	P	navace
083805	083837		1000		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
				19.76	0.53	0.76	1.16	1.48	2.18	S	
				19.72	380	385	629	640	1141	D	t=283-9453
				19.18	185	180	170	177	179	B	
				19.15	2348	2326	2318	2304	2301	R	P=986-3741
				19.12	1024.9	1024.9	1024.5	1024.5	1024.9	P	
084810	084838		1000		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
				19.81	0.52	0.76	1.13	1.49	2.13	S	
				19.77	235	376	686	1.16	1472	D	t=282-9878
				19.69	165	167	169	171	193	B	
				19.67	2353	2381	2381	2384	23	R	P=985-8257
				19.66	1024.1	1024.2	1024.1	1024.4	1024.1	P	
085905	085937		1000		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
				19.73	0.52	0.77	1.10	1.47	2.14	S	
				19.70	378	348	705	892	789	D	t=283-166
				19.74	178	180	180	183	185	B	
				19.80	2391	2377	2369	2359	2345	R	P=984-7243
				19.74	1023.0	1023.0	1023.0	1023.1	1022.8	P	
092005	092034		1000		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
				21.07	0.52	0.76	1.09	1.48	2.11	S	
				20.99	322	230	460	657	1301	D	t=282-0245
				21.19	179	181	180	180	181	B	
				21.22	2333	2330	2359	2372	2381	R	P=981-6129
				21.20	1020.0	1020.1	1020.0	1020.0	1020.0	P	
094820	094852		1000		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
				20.67	0.52	0.73	1.09	1.41	2.08	S	
				20.47	211	287	459	524	606	D	t=282-7675
				20.46	197	197	198	196	201	B	
				20.63	2447	2436	2426	2412	2397	R	P=980-304
				20.40	1018.6	1018.7	1018.6	1018.7	1018.7	P	
101059	101124		100 FL		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
				22.05	0.50	0.75	1.07	1.41	2.03	S	
				21.94	315	652	883	521	7011	D	t=267-1633
				22.14	181	180	180	191	190	B	
				21.62	2347	2349	2350	2353	2356	R	P=695-907
				22.69	977.6	977.7	977.7	977.6	977.9	P	
122323	122352		100 FL		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
				24.50	0.46	0.69	1.04	1.35		S	descended on
				24.70	468	364	556	664		D	5th sat
				25.25	211	211	212	223		B	
				24.75	2480	2478	2484	2488		R	t=263-9089
					967.3	967.7	967.2	967.3		P	P=696-6252

CCN LOG

2 of 4

ALLEVIATOR GMT	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF		1	2	3	4	5	
130030	130101	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.85	0.49	0.68	1.06	1.34	1.95	S
		23.59	412	403	545	615	707	D
		23.60	201	199	195	196	200	B
		23.61	2495	2496	2497	2498	24	R
		23.99	1000.2	1000.2	1002.1	1002.1	1002.1	P
131858	131935	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.64	0.49	0.70	1.05	1.37	1.98	S
		22.51	293	378	965	612	1774	D
		23.29	196	196	195	201	204	B
		23.14	2500	2499	2499	2497	2500	R
		23.10	1002.1	1002.1	1002.2	1002.7	1002.7	P
132758	132827	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		23.29	0.49	0.69	1.08	1.39	1.99	S
		22.94	449	488	624	781	2118	D
		23.17	197	198	199	210	211	B
		23.38	2502	2500	2499	2500	2498	R
		23.37	1003.0	1003.1	1003.2	1003.9	1004.0	P
134031	134102	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.19	0.49	0.70	1.05	1.35	1.96	S
		23.41	526	505	664	918	1914	D
		23.34	189	190	192	198	214	B
		23.15	2498	2496	2496	2497	24	R
		23.04	1005.1	1005.2	1005.1	1005.1	1005.2	P
134935	135004	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.98	0.48	0.71	1.05	1.37	1.95	S
		23.08	625	644	1056	900	1152	D
		23.12	191	194	200	200	209	B
		23.99	2496	2496	2495	2495	2494	R
		23.93	1005.1	1005.1	1005.2	1005.1	1005.1	P
135701	135721	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.63	0.49	0.68	1.04	1.28	2.01	S
		22.62	729	998	1001	2059	4457	D
		22.53	198	201	204	211	212	B
		22.78	2499	2494	2492	2489	2487	R
		22.71	1006.0	1006.1	1006.2	1007.1	1007.1	P
141215	141246	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.42	0.48	0.72	1.06	1.37	2.03	S
		22.93	1029	1048	1753	2404	4078	D
		22.94	228	235	238	241	229	B
		22.82	2485	2492	2499	2503	2506	R
		22.93	1007.0	1007.1	1007.1	1007.1	1007.1	P
142401	142455	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.92	0.49	0.68	1.06	1.37	1.98	S
		22.65	512	1100	1924	2424	4092	D
		23.19	239	245	249	250	248	B
		23.10	2479	2464	2447	2424	2419	R
		23.53	1008.2	1008.1	1008.2	1008.9	1008.7	P

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B136

Date:

29 Sep 2005

Operator:

Doug Anderson

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	Teflon/Nylon/Paper	Bottom inlet	Teflon/Paper
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Transit	120	89	13	Top	07:50:10	08:17:30	Transit	44	Blank run, no pump, sample lines closed
Transit	93	111	154	Bottom	07:50:10	08:18:00	Transit	34	Blank run, no pump, sample lines closed
Filters run1	132	128	16	Top	08:34:10	09:38:05	R6	1244	
Filters run1	50	147	83	Bottom	08:34:10	09:38:05	R6	2436(+60)	Flow reset zero button stuck partly out so and released 08:35:40. Corresponding flow over following 1:30 was 60
Filters run 2	116	54	21	Top	09:41:50	09:58:55	R6	341	
Filters run 2	156	117	143	Bottom	09:41:50	09:58:55	R6	708	
Filters run 3	155	144	23	Top	12:48:50	13:23:40	R11	664	
Filters run 3	123	140	134	Bottom	12:48:50	13:23:40	R11	1215	
Filters run 4	159	52	5	Top	13:25:25	14:03:10	R11	603	
Filters run 4	78	108	126	Bottom	13:25:25	14:03:10	R11	1423	
Filters run 5	121	114	18	Top	14:06:10	14:43:43	R11	719	
Filters run 5	136	101	94	Bottom	14:06:10	14:43:43	R11	1401	
Filters run 6	146	51	58	Top	14:46:54	15:20:40	R11	638	
Filters run 6	96	130	92	Bottom	14:46:54	15:20:40	R11	1270	
Filters run 7	55	139	4	Top	15:23:39	15:54:30	R11	627	
Filters run 7	153	127	115	Bottom	15:23:39	15:54:30	R11	1382	
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					

Flight No. **B136**

Route **Round Britain**

Date **29 September 05**

Take Off **8.45**

Bag Samplers: **Alan McDonald, Davida Farnham**

Sheet No. **1**

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-604	7:50:00	7:50:30			10kft
05-536	53:00	53:34	52.1	1.2	"
05-502	56:00	56:30	52	1.6	"
05-305	59:30	8:00:00	52	1.6	"
05-378	8:19:30	8:20:00	51.4	4.2	6kft
05-270	23:00	23:30		4.5	4kft
05-504	27:00	27:30			2kft (1-3)
05-309	30:00	30:29	n	5.4	500ft
05-370	31:30	32:00			250ft
05-491	34:30	35:00			750ft
05-15	35:30	36:00			
05-118	36:30	37:00			
05-298	37:30	38:00			
05-504	38:30	39:00	51.7	5.4	0.7kft
05-608	39:30	40:00			
05-614	40:30	41:00	51.8	5.4	
* 05-613	41:30	42:00			
690	42:30	43:00			
500	43:30	44:00			
208	44:30	45:00			
232	45:30	46:00	52.2	5.4	0.7kft
412	46:30	47:00			
540	47:30	48:00			
365	48:30	49:00	52.3	5.4	
377	49:30	50:00			
272	50:30	51:00			
560	51:30	52:00			
623	52:30	53:00	52.6	5.4	
360	53:30	54:00			
529	54:30	55:00			
108	55:30	56:00			
39	56:30	57:00			
153	57:30	58:00			
166	58:30	59:00			
278	59:30	9:00:00	53	5.4	
466	9:00:30	9:01:00			Dublin plume
350	01:30	02:00			Dublin plume
438	02:30	03:00			"
302	03:30	04:00			"
284	04:30	05:00			ferry plume?
114	05:30	06:00			

PROFILE 1

(?)

* I don't put 05 anymore as they should all be '05'. Unless they aren't, it won't be specified.

Flight No. B136Route Round G. BritainDate 29/09/2005Take Off 845Bag Samplers: Alan McDonald, Dawela FawcettSheet No. 2

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
375	09:06:30	09:07:00	53.4	5.3	
151	7:30	8:00			
225	8:30	9:00			
395	9:30	10:00			
19	10:30	11:00			
492	11:35	12:05			
308	12:30	13:00			
111	13:35	14:00			
541	14:30	15:00	53.9	5.3	
545	15:30	16:00			
116	16:30	17:00			
352	17:30	18:00			
550	18:30	19:00			
159	19:30	20:00			
629	20:30	21:00	54.3	5.2	
501	21:30	22:00			
547	22:30	23:00			
222	23:30	24:00			
137	24:30	25:00			
548	25:30	26:00			
129	26:30	27:00			
70	27:30	28:00	54.7	5.4	Belfast plume
37	28:30	29:00			
603	29:30	30:00			
353	30:30	31:00			
67	31:30	32:00			
401	32:30	33:00	55	5.6	
344	33:30	34:00			
27	34:30	35:00			
555	35:30	36:00			
139	36:30	37:00			
376	37:30	38:00			
45	38:30	39:00			
439	39:30	40:00			
49	40:30	41:00			
155	41:30	42:00	55.4	6.1	
272	42:30	43:00			clean air
154	43:30	44:00			
23	44:30	45:00			
317	45:30	46:00			
616	46:30	47:00			

Flight No. B136 (B)

Route ROUND BRITAIN

Date 29/9/2005

Take Off 12:00 GMT (FROM INVERNESS)

Bag Samplers: D. FARWELL A. McDONALD

Sheet No. 4

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
85	12:22:00	12:22:35	57.9	3.3W	10,000 ft
559	12:27:00	12:27:30	58.1	2.7W	"
330	12:30:00	30:230			"
148	12:37:00	37:30			6,000 ft
443	12:42:00	42:30			3,000 ft? (at turn)
313	46:30	47:00			250 ft
355	47:30	48:00			Change to 1,000 ft
483	48:30	49:00	58.5	1.5W	Start of Run 1,000 ft
124	49:30	50:00			
297	50:30	51:00			
24	51:30	52:00			
652	52:30	53:00			
465	53:30	54:00			
16	54:30	55:00			
407	55:30	56:00			
198	56:30	57:00	58.0	1.6W	
423	57:30	58:00			Point 75
142	58:30	59:00			
307	59:30	13:00:00			
462	13:00:30	01:00			
525	01:30	02:00			
99	02:30	03:00			
207	03:30	04:00			
262	04:30	05:00			
898	05:30	06:00			
506	06:30	07:00			
428	07:30	08:00			
449	08:30	09:00			
554	09:30	10:00			
199	10:30	11:00	57.1	1.6W	
348	11:30	12:00			
431	12:30	13:00			
535	13:30	14:00			
149	14:30	15:00			
549	15:30	16:00			
432	16:30	17:00			
531	17:30	18:00			
416	18:30	19:00			
498	19:30	20:00			
92	20:30	21:00			
260	21:30	22:00			

Flight No. B136(B)

Route ROUND BRITAIN

Date 29/9/2005

Take Off 17:00 GMT - INVERNESS

Bag Samplers: D. FAMILARI, A. McDONALD

Sheet No. 5

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
440	13:22:30	23:00			
228	23:30	24:00	54.3	1.5W	
389	24:30	25:00			
141	25:30	26:00			
235	26:30	27:00			
465	27:30	28:00			
417	28:31	29:01			
426	29:30	30:00			
450	30:30	31:00			
419	31:30	32:00			
266	32:30	33:00			
533	33:30	34:00			
150	34:30	35:00			
219	35:30	36:00			
547	36:30	37:00			
316	37:30	38:00	55.5	1.2W	
267	38:30	39:02			
202	39:30	40:00			
481	40:30	41:10			
273	41:40	42:10			
197	42:30	43:00			
10	43:30	44:00			
312	44:30	45:00			
263	45:30	46:00			
508	46:30	47:02			
347	47:30	48:00			Point 79
221	48:31	49:02			
294	49:30	50:00			
342	50:30	51:00			
287	51:30	52:00			
201	52:30	53:00			
519	53:30	54:00			
169	54:30	55:00			
397	55:30	56:00			
390	56:30	57:00			
340	57:30	58:00			
006	58:30	59:00			
495	59:30	14:00:00			
447	14:00:30	01:00			
471	01:30	02:00			
475	02:30	03:00			Point 80

Flight No. B136 (B)Route ROUND BRITAINDate 29/9/05Take Off Bag Samplers: D. FAMILIARI , A MCDONALDSheet No. 6

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
046	14:03:30	04:00	54.0	0.0E	P. 130
429	04:30	05:00			
020	05:30	06:00			
112	06:30	07:00			
404	07:30	08:00			
351	08:30	09:00			
654	09:30	10:00			
441	10:30	11:00			
544	11:30	12:00			
320	12:30	13:00			
518	13:30	14:00			
341	14:30	15:00	53.4	0.8E	
old 534	15:30	16:00			
363	16:30	17:00			
459	17:30	18:00			
68	18:30	19:00			
300	19:30	20:00			
247	20:30	21:00			
337	21:30	22:00			
386	22:30	23:00			
75	23:30	24:00			
299	24:30	25:00			
334	25:30	26:00			
324	26:30	27:00			
301	27:30	28:00			
295	28:30	29:00			
436	29:30	30:00			
362	30:30	31:00			
033	32:00	32:30			Tube fell off - loose debris.
659	33:00	33:30			
446	34:00	34:30			
303	35:00	35:30			
367	36:00	36:30			
553	37:00	37:30			
191	38:00	38:30			
523	39:00	39:30			
383	40:00	40:30			
420	41:00	41:30			
410	42:00	42:30			
479	43:00	43:30			
325	44:00	44:30			

Flight No. B136 (B)

Route BY ROUND BRITAIN

Date 29/9/2005

Take Off

Bag Samplers: D. FANULARI , A. McDONALD

Sheet No. 7

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
346	14:45:00	45:30			
368	46:00	46:30			
292	47:00	47:30			
165	48:00	48:30			
415	49:00	49:30			
356	50:00	50:30			
333	51:00	51:30			
212	52:00	52:30			
125	53:00	53:30			
257	54:00	54:30			
144	55:00	55:30			
414	56:00	56:30			
493	57:00	57:30			
286	58:00	58:30			
4088	59:00	59:30			408 marked in bio on bag
264	15:00:00	15:00:30			
167	01:00	01:30			
653	02:00	02:30			
366	03:00	03:30			
546	04:00	04:30			
472	05:05	05:35			
605	06:00	06:30			
289	07:00	07:30			
241	08:00	08:30			
176	09:00	09:30			
244	10:00	10:30			
90	11:30	12:00			Slight problem - resolved
90	12:10	12:40			
369	13:00	13:30			
175	14:00	14:30			
200	15:00	15:30			
319	16:00	16:30			
034	17:00	17:30			
120	18:00	18:30			
036	19:00	19:30			
183	20:00	20:30			
620	21:00	21:30			
138	22:00	22:30			start 22:00
72	23:00	23:30			Point 44.
105	24:00	24:30			
041	25:00	25:30			

Flight No. B136 (B)

Route ROUND BRIMAN

Date 29/9/2005

Take Off

Bag Samplers: D. FAMULARI, A. McDONALD

Sheet No. 8

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
135	15:26:00	26:30			
140	27:00	27:30	50.4N	1.3W	
193	28:00	28:30			
44	29:00	29:30			
494	30:00	30:30			
229	31:00	31:30			
445	32:00	32:30			
606	33:04	33:34			
6065	34:00	34:30			
113	35:00	35:30			
627	36:00	36:30			
339	37:00	37:30			
602	38:00	38:30			
511	39:00	39:30			
035	40:00	40:30			
335	41:00	41:30			
184	42:00	42:30			
458	43:00	43:30			
178	44:00	44:30			
626	45:00	45:30			
619	46:00	46:30			
64	47:00	47:30			
100	48:00	48:30			
528	49:00	49:30			
160	50:00	50:30			
253	51:00	51:30			
156	52:10	52:30	50.0	3.2	
628	53:00	53:30			
516	54:00	54:30			End of Run at 1000 ft
558	15:55:30	16:56:00			Probe down Run at 250ft
618	56:30	57:00			Probing to 5000 ft
157	57:30	58:00			" "
194	16:00:30	16:00:30			" "
115	16:02:30	03:00			Run at 5000 ft
617	03:30	04:00			" "
384	05:00	05:30			" "
130	08:00	08:30			" "
98	16:10:30	11:00			Probing down
543	11:30	12:00			" "
107	16:12:30	13:00			" "
31	16:13:30	14:00			Start of Run 1000 ft (Bright channel)

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: ...B136.....

Date: 29/09/05.....

Campaign Name: ..AMREP / FLUXEX.....

Operator: JIM HOPKINS.....

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
		<p><u>PAN</u> : ARGON PRESSURE $\approx$ 130 bar PAN pump turned on at end of run B136.001 Copper Sulphate $\approx$ 12cm left.</p> <p><u>WAS</u> : cylinder re-filled to $\approx$ 75 bar</p> <p><u>NOTE</u> : Bottle 32 in case 5 cannot be used. - swapped over solenoids in hold to flush case properly.</p> <p>TIME CHECK AT 07:44:30</p> <p>TAKE OFF and ascend to FL100 for NO_x Cals.</p>	
08:15:07		Profile descent to 6000 ft.	
	25	Run 1 @ FL 60 profile descent	3.16
08:20:49		Run 2 @ FL 40 profile descent	
08:26:47		Run 3 @ FL 20 profile descent turning @ WP 49	
08:29:48		Run 4 @ 500 ft profile descent	
		Run 5 @ 250 ft	
08:31:40	26	250ft. climb to 1000ft. turn @ WP 50 Run 6 @ 1000ft.	3.35
08:35:51		WP 5	
08:37:01	27		3.33
08:44:00	28		3.33
08:51:01	29		3.33
08:57:40	30		3.34

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: ...B136.....

Date:29/09/05.....

Campaign Name: ..AMPEP/FLUXEX.....

Operator:Jim Hopkins.....

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
09:02:16	31	In Dublin plume.	3.33
09:09:06	16		3.33
09:17:00	17		3.33
09:22:01	18	In Belfast plume	3.33
09:30:05	19		3.33
09:39:00	20		3.32
09:48:51	21	in very clean air.	3.31
09:57:30	22		3.33
09:58:52		profile down to 250 ft.	
10:00:21	23	Run 7 250 ft. 250 ft.	3.35
10:01:05		profile up to 6000 ft.	
10:07:23	24	Run 8 @ 6000 6500 ft above cloud.	3.14
10:19		air sample pipe closed. WAS pump + compressed air off. Land in Inverness	

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: ...B.136.....

Date: 29/09/05

Campaign Name: AMPPEP/FLUXEX

Operator: JIM HOPKINS

time	Bottle #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
		TAKEOFF from Inverness Sample pipe opened WAS pump and cylinders on. FL100 for NOx Calcs. descend to 6000ft Level Run 9 @ 6000ft ! CASE 4 NOT FLUSHING PROPERLY/AT ALL! - ONLY 16 BOTTLES LEFT FOR REMAINDER OF THE FLIGHT !	
12:34			
12:46:19		Level Run ¹⁰ @ 250 ft	
	41.	250 ft.	3.36
12:48:09		Run 11 @ 1000 ft	
			3.33
12:53:01	42		3.33
			3.33
13:12:05	43		3.32
			3.32
13:30:00	44		3.33
			3.33
13:33:28	45		3.33
13:48:17		WP 79	
13:56:44	46	Teeside plume	?

WAS + PAN sampling summary

Flight number: B136

Date: 29/09/05

Campaign Name: AMPEP/FLUXEX

Operator: JIM HOPKINS

time	Bottle ⑥ #	comments	Final pressure (bar)
14:14:06	47	Humberside plume	3.33
14:26:59		WP 40.	
14:30:00	48	large amounts of ovoc from PTRMS	?
14:44:30	57	Just passed WP 41	3.32
14:53:50	58	NO _x above 10 ppb - London plume.	3.33
14:56:30	59	London plume	3.33
15:13:31	60	lots of oxygenates from PTRMS.	3.33
15:23:11	61	polluted, just before WP 44.	3.33
15:54:26		End of run 11 @ 1000 ft descend to 250 ft Run @ 250 ft	
15:55:45	62	250 ft	3.35
		profile climb to 5000 ft	
16:00:50		Run @ 5000 ft	
16:01:15	63		3.19
16:08:58		Profile 2 descent	
16:12:46		Run 14 @ 1000 ft	
16:19:45	64		3.33
~ 16:50		ascend to FL100 for NO _x calcs air sample pipe closed	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 136

Date: 29th September 2005

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	<u>Probes</u>		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2		n
Heimann		N	HVPS		N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25		N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100		N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		N			
FWVS		N	<u>Racks:</u>		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC		N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI		Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP		N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer		N
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters		y
“ JO1D	Y	y	AMS		Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS		N			
MARSS		N			
DEIMOS		N	<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES		N	NIR TDLAS		N
SWS		N	2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		N
SO2		Y	Formaldehyde		N
NOX		Y	ADA		N
CO		Y	CPI		N
ORAC		N	NOxy		y
PAN		N	PTRMS		y
PERCA		n	Bag Sampling		y
WAS		Y	Tube Sampling		N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B136

Date: 29th September 2005

Instruments

1. TWC not fitted
2. Smudge on Foreward facing camera
3. 2DC – possible contamination of probe during refuelling – laser down on power
4. DRS locked up during preflight – DRS status showed no flight number and recording 'held'. These were set via HORACE terminal screen and appeared to clear properly. This was repeated during fl 100 NOxy cal run and the FM's pc also had problems running the flight summary update. HORACE option 3 had to be used to reboot system. All running programs on pc closed and restarted. The system then ran normally.
5. possible contamination of 2DC during refueling.

Aircraft

1. Airstairs u/s (hydraulic leak).
2. Light in wc failed?

Satcom H Calls nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B136:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Eiko Nemitz
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy
PTrMS	No log is ever taken for PTrMS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :

- 6 x Forward Facing Cameras
- 6 x Rearward Facing Cameras